

METACOGNITIVE STRATEGIES FOR LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES**Bunyatova A.**

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Abstract

In a rapidly changing world, a person's ability to self-learn, self-regulate and make independent decisions is becoming crucial. Spontaneous foreign language speech, as one of the most important aspects of communicative competence, requires students not only to master the lexical and grammatical minimum, but also to have flexible thinking, quick orientation in a communicative situation, and conscious control of their speech activity.

Modern society poses new challenges to citizens of all countries that require them to quickly respond to processes in the world, changing several times faster than the education system. Charles Darwin said that it is not the smartest who survives, but the one who responds best to the changes that are taking place. Only those countries will prosper where people have intellectual and practical skills, and most importantly, have the desire to independently master new skills, for example, to set tasks, find new solutions and master new moral values.

The urgency to quickly change the students' approach to mastering new material has especially increased in the context of the transition to distance learning. The task of foreign language teachers has become several times more complicated, since university programs are aimed at developing professional skills, studying terms and concepts in various areas of a particular field of knowledge in a foreign language. The main difficulty is the fact that a foreign language is taught in the first and second years, and specialization begins only in the third year, so a foreign language teacher has to rely not only on the students' conscious approach to learning new lexical and conceptual components, but also instill in them a desire for self-development. The most important thing for a person engaged in acquiring new knowledge is to study the mechanisms of memory, the processes of memorization and storage of received information, the ability to combine it with more relevant ideas and the search for ways to eliminate stressful conditions, which can also become blockers of the assimilation of knowledge and its timely use.

Thus, the development of metacognitive skills in teaching spontaneous foreign language speech provides a deeper understanding of the language material, promotes the formation of stable speech skills and allows students to become active participants in the educational process.

Keywords: metacognition, translation, culture, foreign languages, different strategies

Introduction. Metacognitive strategies aimed at planning, monitoring and evaluating one's own cognitive activity become indispensable tools in the development of spontaneous speech. Unlike traditional, reproductive teaching of foreign languages, spontaneous speech requires a high degree of awareness from the learner, the ability to self-observe and correct their speech activity "in the moment".

Metacognitive strategies involve the use of various cognitive strategies in combination to more effectively solve problems in foreign language learning. Cognitive strategies are focused on the implementation of cognitive processes, while metacognitive strategies are aimed at their control. Metacognitive strategies help students to recognize themselves as active participants in learning activities and regulate cognitive processes. They include a variety of actions and complex emotional reactions that facilitate the acquisition, understanding, and subsequent application of new knowledge and skills in various learning contexts. As we wrote earlier, metacognitive strategies are an important aspect of metacognition, which encompasses the ability to organize and control one's own learning and cognition process. In the context of foreign language teaching, metacognitive strategies play a significant role in increasing the effectiveness and success of learning.

Metacognitive strategies enable students to be aware of and in control of their learning process. This includes the ability to set goals, plan tasks, evaluate progress, and adjust their efforts when learning a foreign language. They also help students to assess their strengths and weaknesses in foreign language proficiency, which allows them to choose the most appropriate methods and approaches to learning, taking into account their needs. With the help of metacognitive strategies, the student adapts to different methods and contexts of learning, which is especially important in the case of studying a foreign language in different environments and with different teachers. According to M.G. Evdokimova, metacognitive strategies enable students to become aware of the goals and intentions behind their communication. This helps students choose the appropriate communication style depending on whether they want to inform, persuade, entertain, or interact with the interlocutor. In addition, metacognitive strategies allow for a better understanding of the needs, interests and expectations of the audience, help to recognize emotions and manage them in the communication process, which contributes to more constructive and emotionally balanced dialogues. Thus, E.U. Kartseva and D.V. Tavberidze claim that metacognitive strategies develop the analysis of communicative errors

that students can find and correct to improve their communication skills in a foreign language. With the help of these strategies, students can analyze how successful their communication was. They can ask themselves whether their messages were understandable, effective and acceptable to the interlocutor.

Statement of the problem. In a rapidly changing world, where information flows are constantly increasing, there is a growing need to develop students' skills that facilitate independent learning and adaptation to new challenges. One of these skills is metacognitive strategies that provide conscious planning, control and reflection of one's own cognitive activity. However, in educational practice, especially in non-linguistic universities, insufficient attention is still paid to the formation of these strategies, in particular, when teaching spontaneous foreign language speech.

Analysis of recent studies and publications. The concept of metacognition was introduced by J. Flavell in 1979 and has since been actively developed in psychology, pedagogy and linguodidactics. Numerous studies (Livingston, Garafalo and Lester, Merkulov, etc.) emphasize that metacognitive skills contribute to deeper assimilation of material, improved academic performance, and successful professional adaptation. Researchers note that strategies for planning, monitoring, evaluating and correcting learning activities are particularly effective in conditions of independent or distance learning. However, the issues of implementing these strategies in the process of teaching foreign languages, especially in terms of developing spontaneous speech, remain insufficiently developed and require further analysis.

Task Statement. The purpose of this study is to identify effective approaches to the formation of metacognitive strategies in the process of teaching spontaneous foreign language speech to students of non-linguistic specialties. To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set:

- analyze existing theoretical approaches to metacognitive strategies;
- identify the specifics of using these strategies in teaching speaking;
- develop methodological recommendations for the formation of spontaneous speech taking into account metacognitive components;
- conduct an experimental study to test the effectiveness of the proposed methods.

Outline of the Main Material of the Study. The study used methods such as observation, questionnaires, analysis of written and oral responses of students, as well as comparison of results before and after the introduction of metacognitive strategies into the educational process. During the experiment, it was revealed that students who consciously used metacognitive strategies demonstrated higher results in spontaneous speech tasks, showed greater confidence, reflexivity and adaptability in speech situations.

Metacognitive skills play a key role in the learning process when learning a foreign language. This implies the use of a common approach to mastering different languages, including native and non-native, and is

based on the common mechanisms of language functioning. This generalized approach provides a basis for identifying common patterns, comparing, contrasting, and mastering a variety of languages. Students at non-linguistic universities are trained in specialized fields of knowledge, and teaching foreign language communication should be aimed at meeting their professional needs. Metacognitive strategies enable students to recognize the communication skills needed in their future profession and to adapt learning goals and methods accordingly. Learning often involves mastering specialized terminology and language skills related to a particular field of knowledge. Metacognitive strategies can help students learn and apply this terminology more effectively [10].

Researchers studying this area have emphasized the importance of studying different aspects of metacognition. In psychology, the skill of "thinking about thinking" is called metacognition. This term was coined in 1979 by D. Flavel. The American scientist describes "mental activity aimed at understanding the processes of thinking." (quoted in Livingston) Garafalo and Lester argue that metacognition has two separate but closely related aspects: a) knowledge and understanding of the concept of cognition; b) control and awareness of mental activity. In essence, metacognitive skills can be considered the ability to think about one's own thinking, which is important in solving almost any problem. Today, there are already many studies confirming the importance of this skill in learning and any practical activity. Research shows that "metacognition helps to understand the meaning of what is being studied, which makes it possible to consider metacognitive skills as the basis for successful learning" [8].

I.P. Merkulov attaches decisive importance to the discussed skills in his work "Cognitive Abilities", he writes: "... cognitive activity, which underlies people's desire for knowledge, refers to the fundamental, species-specific behavioral characteristics of a person, ensuring his survival as a biological being. "Human cognition means the search for and acquisition of new knowledge, the creation of some new adaptively valuable cognitive (including cultural) information that would increase the adaptability of people and their chances of survival." [9, p. 11]

The aim of the study is to develop metacognitive skills that can be used by everyone on an ongoing basis to successfully solve learning problems in a difficult situation that has arisen naturally as a result of the pandemic. The need has become even more pressing with the transition of education partially to an online format, where the priority is given to the educational process based on the principles of self-organization. Using our extensive experience in communicating and motivating students, we have incorporated the most basic strategies for solving problematic tasks, well-studied by both domestic and foreign researchers, including the following elements proposed in 1957 by Polya:

1. Assessment, understanding and analysis of the task.
2. Planning, setting goals and subgoals of one's own intellectual activity, thinking through the means of

their implementation, building a sequence of one's own actions, etc.

3. Completing the task.

4. Evaluating, checking and understanding the results of what has been done.

The experimental part of the work included the following methodological techniques:

1) The dialogic form of teaching, which is often used in teaching a foreign language, is essential for the development of metacognitive skills, since in the process of dialogue students can reason about how they learn, how they acquire new skills and how they obtain information. They do not simply answer the teacher's questions about the information they have read, but learn to pose them to themselves - the teacher only stimulates the discussion.

2) Conducting surveys (a survey was conducted of two groups of students: first and second years), who were to take part in the English language Olympiad in a week. The first group was simply informed about the upcoming Olympiad, while the participants in the second group took a 15-minute survey. They were asked what place they expected to take, how they would prepare for the upcoming Olympiad, and whether they planned to participate in all three rounds.

As a result, the overall level of assessments in the second group was 10% higher than in the first. We assume that the students from the second group used their metacognitive skills more strongly. They had to think through the process of preparing for the upcoming Olympiad in advance and develop a certain action plan. In other words, the survey prompted them to start monitoring their mental activity.

3) Analysis of test results, when it is possible to track both individual and group errors, and then choose ways to eliminate them depending on the students' abilities and priorities.

4) Written analysis of what was the most difficult for successfully eliminating errors. The procedure for assessing the results of this work took place both in a group (students of the group expressed their opinions on the work of one of the participants in completing the task) and in an individual format, when the teacher orally or in writing assessed the students' work, comparing the contribution of each and explaining their strengths and weaknesses. The surveys we conduct weekly at the end of online classes, as well as during midterm assessments, as well as the results of exams, competitions, participation in scientific conferences where students became winners - all this allowed us to appreciate the effectiveness of the development of metacognitive skills.

It is worth noting that more capable students who take a conscious approach to their learning have more developed metacognitive skills. Several students decided to take part in a scientific conference within the university in order to improve their performance, and, according to our observations, highly motivated students most often practically independently coped with the above-described tasks, which are elements of metacognition.

They were able not only to choose a topic for conducting scientific research, go through all the stages

necessary for conducting the research, but were also not afraid to participate in an international scientific competition, first taking third place within the university, and then, having worked a little, got the chance to send the work to an international scientific research competition at the International Center for Scientific Partnership, where they rightfully took first place among the best research papers of 2022. Of course, the role of the teacher in this case is not diminished, but when working with undergraduate and graduate students in economics or ecology, it would be difficult for a foreign language teacher to find relevant research topics. However, working at a university and being not only a teacher but also a researcher, many specialists are able to provide scientific guidance, set a goal, think through the sequence of actions when completing tasks, evaluate and check the results of the work done, and, if necessary, motivate to achieve more ambitious goals. Unfortunately, such work is very low valued in universities, essentially being an additional burden. Summing up the results of the study and assessing the achievements of their students, it is worth noting that "the use of information technology in completing all kinds of tasks that are immediately checked and assessed leads to even greater independence, develops critical thinking, involves students in educational activities." [1]

Nevertheless, in our opinion, technologies are only a tool that provides significant and invaluable assistance in the implementation of most routine tasks, and one of the most urgent and primary goals facing modern education is the development and use of a methodological culture learners in terms of their independent acquisition and assimilation of knowledge and skills. In the process of self-training and self-development, metacognitive skills play an important role, which are professionally significant qualities of a modern future specialist. According to many teachers, the development of metacognitive skills can significantly improve the quality of education not only in universities, but also in self-education, and will also help in solving pressing life problems.

The term "metacognition" first appeared in psychology, and then began to be used in linguistics and teaching methods. In psychology, metacognition is understood as "thinking about thinking". J. Flavel introduced the concept of metacognition, understanding it as a special cognitive process aimed at understanding one's own cognitive activity [3]. In other words, metacognitive skills are the ability to think about one's own thinking, and this is of great importance in solving almost any problem. He identified four key components: metacognitive knowledge, metacognitive experience, cognitive goals and tasks, and cognitive strategies. An important issue is the distinction between cognitive and metacognitive strategies: Based on the functions they perform, they have so many substantive differences, says J. Flavel.

In his opinion, metacognitive strategies differ from cognitive ones not so much in content as in goals: cognitive strategies are aimed at performing cognitive tasks, while metacognitive ones are aimed at controlling these tasks. Sometimes metacognitive strategies

are attributed to effective strategies and social strategies for interaction with the study group and native speakers. Since metacognitive and cognitive strategies of the text are interrelated, studying one without taking into account the other may be ineffective. L.S. Vygotsky theorized and expanded the structure of the concept of metacognition. He developed a psychological concept that combines signs (words), society (communication) and activity (business) into a single theoretical whole [7].

Thus, metacognition involves understanding the structures of cognitive processes and the ability to orient and control thinking using symbols and signs. Thus, a student can achieve his goals both individually and under the guidance of a teacher. The teacher takes responsibility for monitoring, setting goals, planning and directing attention. Gradually, this responsibility passes to the student, which corresponds to the metacognitive development described by L.S. Vygotsky. When we talk about introducing new approaches and methods into the process of teaching students, we mean the integration of metacognitive strategies into the educational process of learning a foreign language. Strategies for mastering a foreign language can be divided into two levels:

- cognitive, related to the processing and assimilation of educational information (for example, strategies for repetition, elaboration and organization of material);
- metacognitive, which concern the organization of educational activities and their management, such as strategies for planning, observation and regulation.

According to I.P. Merkulov, students of non-linguistic universities should be able to effectively communicate in academic environments, including discussions, writing scientific papers and reports. Given the international context of study, students must be prepared to interact with colleagues and partners from different countries. Strategies help them to recognize differences in intercultural communication and adapt their communication according to these differences. J. Harmer argues that the ability to speak fluently involves not only knowledge of the language features, but also the ability to process information and language instantly. He also argues that in the process of learning to speak or developing foreign language speech skills, it is necessary to consider three important sections: the new language, practice, and communicative activity [9].

The ability to speak correctly and quickly is important for career success. Speaking skills can improve social life, thereby ensuring the all-round growth that everyone should strive for. D. Noonan argues that speech is an important and effective tool for communicating with others.

Spontaneous speech is often used in the process of learning a foreign language and plays an important role in the development of metacognitive skills. During communication, students can reflect on how they learn, how they improve their skills, and how they acquire new information. They go beyond simply answering the teacher's question about the material they have read,

and learn to ask questions and initiate discussions, with the teacher acting as a facilitator of discussion.

Students who demonstrate the ability to approach their learning mindfully tend to have more advanced metacognitive skills. Based on our observations, it can be stated that highly motivated students often successfully completed the assigned tasks independently [6]. It is important to note that metacognition is a type of higher cognitive thinking that includes the ability to control cognitive processes, which characterizes its high level. Metacognitive skills are developed through work with text material and during speech in a foreign language. For this purpose, various speaking exercises are included, aimed at solving information processing problems. In modern textbooks and special manuals for developing speech skills, such exercises are usually aimed at developing semantic, cognitive and creative thinking. These semantic tasks are offered to students in exercises to check understanding of the content of the material by creating oral statements on the topic and other types of speech activity. We propose to consider metacognitive strategies using the example of tasks for teaching one of the types of speech activity - speaking (spontaneous communication) in the process of learning a foreign language.

1. Goal. When teaching spontaneous foreign language communication - to develop awareness and control over one's own language process. Tasks may include setting language goals; reflecting on one's own progress to achieve linguistic achievements in real communication situations.

2. Planning. In the context of spontaneous communication in language learning, planning strategies include identifying conversation goals, choosing topics for discussion, and preparing key expressions or phrases in advance. This helps students feel more confident in speaking and use language resources more effectively. Here is an example of an assignment for students: write down specific goals for speaking practice (e.g., "learn to express your thoughts on the topic of health"); choose a topic for discussion and justify your choice, demonstrating planning skills; create a conversation plan, including key phrases or questions to support the dialogue; at the end of speaking practice, ask students to evaluate their success, identifying strengths and areas for improvement.

3. Evaluation and correction. Evaluation and correction are carried out through analysis and other forms of control: students are asked to exchange feedback, highlighting successful moments and offering constructive comments to improve speech; task to analyze frequently occurring errors, identifying patterns for subsequent correction. It is important to note that the assessment should be perceived as a tool for developing and improving the effectiveness of communications, and not just as an assessment of students' performance.

According to U.S. Belenkova, the choice of metacognitive strategies in learning means that the student structures his actions, promoting the development of the desire for independent knowledge. It is important to note the problem associated with the difficulties of assessing the mastery of metacognitive strategies in

teaching a foreign language. Students with highly developed metacognitive skills engage in meaningful activities to understand their process using a variety of strategies compared to less experienced students using their metacognitive skills [2].

Metacognitive knowledge about task characteristics (e.g. what is needed to solve problems) and the use of appropriate strategies to solve them are considered key factors in effective language learning. This is due to the fact that metacognitive strategies allow students to actively participate in the learning process, managing their learning and finding optimal ways to consolidate the material they have learned. These skills provide an advantage, improving the ability to process and remember new information, which ultimately leads to higher performance on tests, improved learning outcomes, and higher achievement. According to T.O. Nelson, students who have a stable system of strategies reveal metacognitive knowledge about their individual methods of thinking and learning, understand learning tasks and can better apply strategies that correspond to the tasks set, optimally using their individual potential [5].

Conclusions. The development of educational programs for mastering metacognitive strategies of spontaneous foreign language speech is a key stage in modern education, contributing to more effective language learning. These programs are aimed at an in-depth understanding of metacognitive processes. Their implementation promotes the development of linguistic flexibility and confidence in communication in practice. The level of confidence not only improves communication skills, but also promotes the development of critical thinking and understanding of cultural characteristics. Students gain the ability to adapt to a variety of language situations, demonstrating flexibility in the choice of expressive means and effectiveness in communicating with native speakers. As a result, this not only improves the level of proficiency in a foreign language, but also forms a deep understanding. Thus, metacognitive strategies aimed at teaching spontaneous foreign language speech are exciting and diverse studies. When learning a new language, there is an immersion in its sound and structural features. Starting with the study of individual words, students gradually move on to phrases and short statements and ultimately to direct communication in a foreign language.

The process of learning a foreign language is compared to mastering a new game, where learning the rules or observing the game is accompanied by the key role of listening. The development of needs for using a foreign language stimulates regular conversations with others, which is an integral part of metacognitive strategies. This not only promotes the practical application of language skills, but also integrates into the learning process a conscious analysis and assessment of one's language knowledge and level of language acquisition. As a result, students not only improve their communicative competence, but also develop the ability to reflect, which raises the effectiveness of language learning to a higher level. Research on metacognitive strategies in the context of teaching spontaneous foreign language speech provides extensive prospects for future research. Studying these strategies may shed more

light on the process of self-regulation and planning in language learning, as well as their impact on spontaneous language interaction. Future research may deepen our understanding of which specific metacognitive strategies have been found to promote spontaneous foreign language speech.

The obtained results confirm the high efficiency of integrating metacognitive strategies into the process of teaching spontaneous foreign language speech. Students with a developed level of metacognitive awareness are able to plan their speech activity more effectively, correct errors and independently develop language competence. Thus, the formation of metacognitive skills should become an important component of the methodology of teaching foreign languages in non-linguistic universities. This will ensure not only a higher level of language proficiency, but also the development of critical thinking, communicative flexibility and the ability to learn independently.

References:

1. Armstrong S.J. The influence of individual cognitive style on performance in management education / S.J. Armstrong // *Educational Psychology*. – 2000. – Vol. 20 (3). – P. 323-339.
2. Belenkova U.S. Obuchenie metacognitivnym navyam I metody otsenki ih sformirovannosti. Gumanitarnye, sotsyalno ekonomicheskie I obshestvennye nauki. [Metacognitive skills training and methods of their maturity evaluation. Humanitarian, socio-economic and social sciences] / U. S. Belenkova // *Nauka I obrazovanie* [Science and education]. – Krasnodar, 2015 – № 3-2. – P. 20-22.
3. Flavell J.H. Metacognition and cognitive monitoring: A new area of cognitive-development inquiry/J.H. Flavell // *Amer. Psychologist*. – 1979. – Vol. 34. – P. 906-911.
4. Gavrilina L.E. Ispolzovanie informatsionnyh tehnologiy v sovremennom obrazovanii pri obuchenii inostrannomu yazyku [Application of information technologies in modern education in foreign language training] / L. E. Gavrilina // *Teoreticheskie I prikladnye voprosy obrazovaniya I nauki* [Theoretical and applied issues of science and education]. – Ukom. – Tambov, 2014. – Pt. 13. – P. 40-42.
5. Hartman H.J. Metacognition in Learning and Instruction: Theory, Research, and Practice / H.J. Hartman. – Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers, 2001.
6. Holodnaya M.A. Psihologiya intellekta; paradoksy issledovaniya [Psychology of Intelligence: paradoxes of research]/M.A.Holodnaya.–Saint-Petersburg : Piter, 2002.
7. Holodnaya M.A. Kognitivnye stili. O prirode individulnogo uma [About the nature of individual intellect]/M.A. Holodnaya. – Saint-Petersburg: Piter, 2004.–384 p.
8. Livingston J.A. Metacognition: An Overview / J.A. Livingston. – New York, 2003. [Electronic-resource].
URL:https://www.researchgate.net/publication/234755498_Metacognition_An_Overview. (accessed: 13.06.2022).

9. Merkulov I.P. *Cognitivnye sposobnosti [Cognitive abilities]* / I.P. Merkulov. – Moscow, 2005. – 182 p.

10. Zimmerman B.J. *Investigating self-regulation and motivation: Historical Background, methodological developments, and future prospects* / B.J. Zimmerman // *American Educational Research Journal*. – 2008. – № 45 (1). – P. 166–183.